

KWAME NKURUMAH UNIVERSITY OF SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY, KUMASI

COLLEGE OF SCIENCE

DEPARTMENT OF PHYSICS

**Biophysics Osteoarthritis of the Lateral Compartment with Valgus Knee Deformity
(Knock-Knee): A Case Study among some Elderly Ghanaian Women within an Urban
Orthopaedic Practice**

BY

Celestine Segbefia

(BSc. Hons)

A THESIS SUBMITTED TO THE DEPARTMENT OF PHYSICS, KWAME
NKURUMAHY UNIVERSITY OF SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY IN PARTIAL
FULFILMENT OF THE REQUIREMENTS FOR THE AWARD OF

MASTER OF PHILOSOPHY

IN

NUCLEAR PHYSICS

Supervisor: Mr Eric Kotei Addison

August, 2018

ABSTRACT

This study presents the results on biophysics osteoarthritis of the lateral compartment with valgus knee deformity (knock-knee) in a case study among some elderly Ghanaian women. The study was conducted on 90 adult female patients, ages 40 to 81 years, with a mean age of 56.24 ± 1.06 years and a mean body mass index of 24.85 ± 0.09 kg/m². Seventy-nine (79) of the patients were employed, grouped into four (4) categories; farming (29), trading (38), teaching (5), and others; which included catering (1), civil servant (2), nursing (1), seamstress (1), housewife (1), and a retiree (1). Six (6) of the patients were unemployed, and there were no records of employment for five (5) of them. Radiographic images of each patient were taken to the nearest 1 degree using the golden rule hip-knee-ankle measurement to determine the tibiofemoral angle and mechanical angle deviation. Using the resultant force theory, the magnitude of the force component in the x and y directions was determined. The level of severity of the deformity was also determined by considering the normal valgus angle of 10 degrees to the mechanical angle deviation. Forty-one (41) percent showed higher levels of deformity, and fifty-nine (59) percent showed minimal levels of deformity when compared to the mean mechanical angle of 18.05 ± 0.95 degrees. Forty-eight (48) patients were affected on the right knees, and forty-two (42) were affected on the left knees. The site of the defect was predicted to be the joint placed under repetitive stress, therefore more force was exerted on the knee joints which causes onset and progression of the deformity. Therefore, this study supports the hypothesis that strenuous occupation is a risk factor of valgus knee deformity but age and weight are not risk factors.

TABLE OF CONTENTS

DECLARATION	i
CERTIFICATION	i
ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS	iii
ABSTRACT	iv
LIST OF FIGURES	vi
LIST OF TABLES	vii
LIST OF ABBREVIATION	ix
CHAPTER 1	1
1.1 INTRODUCTION	1
1.2 Background	1
1.3 Problem statement	7
1.4 Justification	8
1.5 Significance of the research	9
1.6 General Objective	10
1.6.1 Specific objectives	10
1.7 Limitations of study	10
1.8 Organisation of thesis	11
CHAPTER 2	12
LITERATURE REVIEW	12
2.1 Introduction	12
2.2 Definition of osteoarthritis	12
2.3 Incidence and prevalence of osteoarthritis	13
2.4 Risk factors	15
2.4.1 Person-level risk factors	16
2.4.2 Joint-level risk factors	20
2.5 Symptoms of osteoarthritis	23
2.6 Diagnosis	24
2.7 Treatment	25
2.7.1 Non-surgical treatment	26
2.7.2 Orthoses and footwear	28
2.7.3 Pharmacotherapy	28
2.8 Surgical treatment	29
2.8.1 Corrective osteotomy	29
2.8.2 Partial or total knee replacement	30
2.8.3 Natural remedies (herbal medicine)	30
CHAPTER 3	31

THEORY	31
CHAPTER 4	33
METHODOLOGY	33
4.0 Introduction	33
4.1 Study setting	33
4.2 Study population	33
4.3 Radiographic measurements	34
4.4 Ethical considerations	36
CHAPTER 5	37
5.1 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION	37
CHAPTER 6	52
CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION.....	52
6.1 CONCLUSION	52
6.2 RECOMMENDATIONS	53
6.2.1 Policy making	53
6.2.2 Further research on the study	53
REFERENCES	54
APPENDICES	64
Appendix A.....	64
Table 1: Index, age, weight, angle, force, height and occupation of subjects.....	64
Table 2: X-component force, Y-component force, RF, and BMI.....	68
Appendix B	72
Java code used for computing component forces	72
Appendix C.....	73
QUESTIONNAIRE	73

LIST OF FIGURES

FIGURE 1. 1: ANATOMY OF THE KNEE	3
FIGURE 1. 2: DEFORMITY OF MECHANICAL AXIS AND JOINT LINE OF LOWER LIMB (BROUWER, ET AL., 2007).....	5
FIGURE 1. 3: WEIGHT-BEARING ANTERIOR RADIOGRAPH OF VALGUS KNEE DEFORMITY SOURCE: ST. JOHN OF GOD HOSPITAL AT DUAYAW NKWANTA IN GHANA.	8
FIGURE 2. 1: AGE AND SEX-SPECIFIC INCIDENCE RATES (/1000 PERSON-YEARS) OF KNEE OSTEOARTHRITIS (BLACK), HIP OSTEOARTHRITIS (RED), AND HAND OSTEOARTHRITIS	

(GREEN). ALL POPULATION; SHORT DASH LINE, WOMEN; LONG DASH LINE, MEN (ALHAMBRA, ET AL., 2014; ALLEN & GOLIGHTLY, 2015).	15
FIGURE 2. 2: PATHOGENESIS OF OA WITH PUTATIVE RISK FACTORS. (ZHANG & JORDAN, 2010).	23
FIGURE 2. 3: AN OFF-LOADER BRACE THAT HELPS TO RE-ALIGN A CORRECTABLE DEFORMITY. (HUSSAIN ET AL, 2016).....	28
FIGURE 3. 1: INDICATING THE WEIGHT EXERTED ON BOTH LEGS WHILE STANDING	31
FIGURE 4. 1: MECHANICAL AXIS OF DEVIATION OF WEIGHT-BEARING ANTERIOR POSTERIOR RADIOGRAPH OF VALGUS KNEE DEFORMITY MEASURED AT 45.1°	35
FIGURE 4. 2: ANATOMICAL TIBIOFEMORAL ANGLE OF WEIGHT-BEARING ANTERIOR POSTERIOR RADIOGRAPH OF VALGUS KNEE DEFORMITY MEASURED AT 21.9°	36
FIGURE 5. 1: TIBIOFEMORAL ANGLE AGAINST SHEAR FORCE FOR FARMERS	39
FIGURE 5. 2: TIBIOFEMORAL ANGLE AGAINST FORCE FOR TRADERS.....	41
FIGURE 5. 3: TIBIOFEMORAL ANGLE AGAINST FORCE FOR TEACHERS.....	43
FIGURE 5. 4: TIBIOFEMORAL ANGLE AGAINST FORCE FOR OTHERS	45
FIGURE 5. 5: GROUP OF OCCUPATION AGAINST WEIGHTED AVERAGE FORCE.....	47
FIGURE 5. 6: TIBIOFEMORAL ANGLE AGAINST AGE.....	48
FIGURE 5. 7: TIBIOFEMORAL ANGLE AGAINST WEIGHT.....	50

LIST OF TABLES

TABLE 5. 1: OCCUPATION AND CORRESPONDING NUMBER OF PATIENTS.	38
TABLE 5. 2: DATA REPRESENTING MEAN AND STANDARD ERROR OF THE PARAMETERS USED IN THE ANALYSIS.....	38
TABLE 5. 3: REGRESSION ANALYSIS FOR FARMERS	40
TABLE 5. 4: DESCRIPTIVE ANALYSIS FOR FARMERS	40
TABLE 5. 5: REGRESSION ANALYSIS FOR TRADERS.....	42
TABLE 5. 6: DESCRIPTIVE ANALYSIS FOR TRADERS	42
TABLE 5. 7: REGRESSION ANALYSIS FOR TEACHERS.....	44
TABLE 5. 8: DESCRIPTIVE ANALYSIS FOR TEACHERS	44
TABLE 5. 9: REGRESSION ANALYSIS FOR OTHERS.....	46

TABLE 5. 10: DESCRIPTIVE ANALYSIS FOR OTHERS	46
TABLE 5. 11: REGRESSION ANALYSIS FOR FARMERS	49
TABLE 5. 12: REGRESSION ANALYSIS FOR FARMERS	50

LIST OF ABBREVIATION

OA.....	Osteoarthritis
US.....	United States
CDC.....	Centre for Disease Control
WHO.....	World Health Organization
JSN.....	Joint Space Narrowing
MRI.....	Magnetic Resonance Imaging
BML.....	Bone Marrow Lesion
NADW.....	National Arthritis Data Workgroup
UK.....	United Kingdom
GDF.....	Growth Differentiation Factor
TKR.....	Total Knee Replacement
ESR.....	Erythrocyte Sedimentation Rate
CRP.....	C - reactive protein
CBC.....	Complete Blood Count
ADL.....	Activity of Daily Living
HRQoL.....	Health-Related Quality of Life
SME.....	Self -Management Education
BMI.....	Body Mass Index
NSAIDs.....	Non-steroid Anti-Inflammatory Drugs
DMARDs.....	Disease Modifying Anti-Rheumatic Drugs
CG.....	Centre of Gravity
AP.....	Anterior Posterior
HANES.....	Health and Nutrition Examination Survey
KG.....	Kilogram

CHAPTER 1

1.1 INTRODUCTION

This chapter introduces the concepts of biophysics osteoarthritis with valgus knee deformity, the prevalence, burdens and management of osteoarthritis. It also contains the problem statement, justification of the study and the main objective of the research.

1.2 Background

Valgus deformity of the knee (“knock-knee”) also referred to as genu valgum is a common condition in which the bone segment distal to a joint is shifted outward, that is, angled laterally away from the body’s medial line. The opposite of this deformity is called varus, a condition in which the bone distal to a joint is bent inwardly. Valgus deformity is commonly found in young children and often corrects naturally as they grow. It had been reported that approximately seventy-five (75) percent of children ranging from ages three (3) to five (5) years had knock-knees. Another report had indicated that in about 99 percent of these cases, valgus deformity corrects naturally by the time the affected children reach age 7 or 8. (Boston Children’s Hospital reports). Nonetheless, this condition may continue or develop later in life and affect the elderly. Usually, valgus knee deformity or “knock-knee” is as a result of arthritis of the knee. People with this condition had their knees touching and the feet are separating from each other as shown in fig. 1.3. When valgus deformities become severe, a lot of stress is placed on the articular cartilage, bone and ligament of the knee joint which causes development of knee osteoarthritis.

Knee osteoarthritis is a trivial degenerative joint disorder affecting the older population. It had become a widely recognized type of joint disease and one of the leading causes of chronic disabilities in these populaces. It is defined pathologically by changing of the entire joint

structure, including progressive degradation of cartilage, menisci and ligaments, synovial inflammation and changes to the subchondral bone. (Issa et al, 2006). According to Felson et al, 2003, in about twenty-five (25) percent of the population who are fifty (55) years or more experience pain in the knee during most days in a month and almost half of them had radiographic osteoarthritis of the knee, a group who were described to had symptomatic osteoarthritis. Osteoarthritis of the knee is seen to be dominant among women than men. Some of the causes associated with knee osteoarthritis are obesity, knee injury, history of knee surgery and, occupation which includes physical activities such as bending, climbing stairs and heavy lifting of loads. It is believed that knee osteoarthritis can also be part of a generalized diathesis, involving osteoarthritis of the hand, which may be heritable (Felson et al, 2003).

According to a study group in the United States (U.S), Centre for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC), the number of persons in the United States diagnosed of knee osteoarthritis was estimated to be about forty-six (46) million, twenty-two (22) percent of which belong to elderly class and this figure is expected to double in the year 2020 as a result of commonness in obesity and ageing of the populace. (Centres for Disease Control and Prevention, 2006), (Hosnijeh et al, 2015). Mane et al, 2000 had also suggested in their study that about eleven (11) percent of the population who are sixty-four (64) years and more had symptomatic OA of the knee. Signs of osteoarthritis are usually seen at age forty-five (45) with the disease slowly progressing with radiographic evidence in the majority of the population by age sixty-five (65) years and in about eighty (80) percent of the population age seventy-five (75) years and more (Manek et al, 2000).

All joint structures within the knee are commonly affected by osteoarthritis. This is evident by hyaline articular cartilage lost, bony remodelling, capsular stretching and weakness of periarticular muscles. Osteoarthritis includes the joint in a non-uniform and focal way. Confined regions of loss of ligament can cause incremental focal stress across the joint

resulting in additional ligament loss. When the region of ligament loss is large enough or bony remodelling occurs; the joint becomes tilted and misaligned. This mostly becomes a potential risk factor for structural distortion of the joint. (Felson et al, 2003).

The knee is the joint that supports almost all the whole weight of the body, hence if more load is exerted on the joint, it makes the knee susceptible to the development of osteoarthritis. The ligaments, bones, meniscus, and tendons constitute the make-up of the knee. Three joint compartments merge to form the knee which includes; the lateral tibia-femoral compartment, the medial tibia-femoral compartment, and the patellar-femoral compartment and the presence of menisci, which contribute more importantly in the transfer of contact stresses from one articular surface to another as shown in figure 1.1. The source of pain accompanied with osteoarthritis may come from any of these three compartments but the patellar-femoral joint is usually affected by this pain. Even though the patellar-femoral joint is an important part of the knee, the primary focus of this study is the tibia-femoral forces.

Figure 1. 1: Anatomy of the knee

In theory, the mechanism of malalignment is any deviation from the neutral alignment of the hip, knee, and ankles which affects load distribution at the knee. The load-bearing axis represents a line drawn from the middle of the femoral head to the middle of the ankle. In a varus alignment knee, the line passes through the medial region of the knee, and creates a moment arm which increases the forces across the medial tibiofemoral compartment. With knock-knee or valgus alignment knee, as described before, represents a line that passes through the lateral portion of the knee and a moment arm is created which increases forces across the lateral tibiofemoral compartment. In a neutrally aligned knee, the medial compartment of the knee joint bears approximately sixty (60) to eighty (80) percent of the compressive loads and, any small changes in the knee alignment brings about abnormal load distribution across the knee. Typically, a four (4) to six (6) percent increase in varus alignment had shown increased loading in the medial compartment by up to twenty (20) percent. (Tetsworth et al, 1994). And according to Felson et al, 2013, like varus malalignment, knees that already had osteoarthritis and whose limbs demonstrate valgus malalignment are at higher risk of joint space loss and cartilage damage on the lateral side of the joint. But from a biomechanical perspective, valgus knees and varus knees are not the same. When in static position, the limb may appear valgus, but in an stance such as walking, the ground reaction force vector which draws from the centre of mass of the body, passes medially to the knee in most patients with valgus knees, and this creates a varus moment. (Felson et al., 2013). The deformity is illustrated in figure 1.2.

Figure 1. 2: Deformity of mechanical axis and joint line of lower limb (Brouwer, et al., 2007).

In a normal valgus knee deformity, normal alignment in distal end of femur, makes an angle of 170-175 degrees (5-10 degrees) with the anatomical axis. However, with excessive valgus deformity (knock-knees), the measured angle lateral is less than 165 degrees (which is equivalent to genu valgus angle of 15 degrees or more) in which the feet are separated from each other than the knee.

Osteoarthritis of the knee varies considerably with its history. While the disease seems to improve in some patients, some of them experience stable conditions and others demonstrate worse conditions. (Felson, 2006). Osteoarthritis reduces the activities of daily living and quality of life. It is estimated twenty-five (25) percent of people with knee osteoarthritis had pain on ambulation and go through a lot of challenges while engaging in major activities of daily living (ADLs) such as walking, climbing stairs, and kneeling or stooping. About fifteen (15) percent of these people use an assistive device such as a cane or crutch when walking. The

modern treatment for symptomatic hip or knee osteoarthritis includes holistic assessment and selection from various options such as lifestyle interventions and education to oral medication and joint replacement surgery. According to Centres for Disease Control and prevention (CDC) report in 2004, osteoarthritis and other associated arthritic conditions cost the United States (U.S.) economy almost \$ 81 billion (about GH¢ 388,395,000,000.00) per year in direct medical care, with indirect expenses of about \$ 47 billion (about GH¢ 225,365,000,000.00) with inclusion such as lost wages and production. The total annual cost of osteoarthritis and related conditions per patient had been estimated to be approximately \$ 1,752 (about GH¢ 8400.84).

Osteoarthritis is highly prevalent and on the rise. A lot of researches had been carried-out in the developed countries concerning this disability. Bold and innovative actions had been taken to limit and prevent the persistent problems created by this ever-growing public health issue. However, in Ghana, no significant research activity had been carried-out so far to help understand the burden of osteoarthritis, the causes associated with it, its prevalent rate and effective strategies for intervention. According to Dr. Prosper K. Moh, a Ghanaian orthopaedic surgeon at Duayaw Nkwanta, valgus osteoarthritis of the knee is more frequent amongst women and usually affects the right knee. (Private communication, 2018).

Ghana is an independent country with a population currently estimated to be 29.46 million. Out of this population, approximately forty (40) percent of the population is made up of individuals aged fifty-five (55) years or older (Report, Ghana demographics). The country is made up of ten (10) regions in which the socioeconomic development, lifestyle factors, environmental factors and healthcare facilities varies greatly amongst residents in the different regions of Ghana. Also, occupational activities of these residents vary considerably. Thus, the overall goal of the present study is to analyse the radiographic images of osteoarthritis of the lateral compartment with valgus knee deformity amongst Ghanaian elderly women and also determine

the occupational relationship and the effect of loading on the lateral compartment of the knee joints.

1.3 Problem statement

When the knee is not in a proper alignment from each side, either Valgus or Varus malalignment occur. Valgus knee or “knock-knee” is commonly defined as arthritis of the knee which causes the knee to bend inward as shown in figure 1.3. Valgus malalignment causes the load distribution of the leg to shift towards the outside. When the knee is severely deformed, a lot of stress is put on the articular cartilage, bone and ligaments of the knee joint which results in the progression of the disease.

The kinematics, anatomy, and loading during movement vary considerably between lateral and medial compartments of the knee. Evidence had indicated that the lateral compartment is mostly affected in about ten (10) percent of people who are affected with osteoarthritis of the knee. The study of the causes of lateral compartment osteoarthritis of the knee can be idiopathic (unknown), generally affecting the femur, or secondary to trauma commonly affecting the tibia. (Scott et al, 2013). Valgus knee deformities had intrinsic complications. If the Valgus knee deformity is corrected, the patella can sub-lux laterally. More often, correction of the deformity can cause limitation or stretch the peroneal nerve. To combat this condition, it will be appropriate to analyse the radiographic images and determine the risk factors associated with this disability in Ghana. Till date, no osteoarthritis study had been carried-out in Ghana hence this study would serve as a first step in the management of the disease in Ghana.

Figure 1. 3: Weight-bearing anterior radiograph of valgus knee deformity Source: St. John of God Hospital at Duayaw Nkwanta in Ghana.

1.4 Justification

The knee is the weight bearing joint that carries almost all weight of the body and is the most commonly affected joint by osteoarthritis. If the knee is perfectly aligned, the load bearing axis represent a line that extends from the hip, through to the knee and ankle joints. But if the knee is not in a proper alignment because of a deformity that is associated with cartilage damage, abnormal force is applied to specific areas of the knee which causes severe pains and other symptoms. Several studies had associated increased joint loading to progression of knee osteoarthritis. Also, the development of knee osteoarthritis had been attributed to other multiple risk factors including mal-alignment and occupations that demand squatting, climbing of stairs, and heavy lifting of loads. It is believed that loading of the knee joint primarily depends on the physical activity. It is acquired when doing most strenuous and frequent activities of daily living (ADL). It can also be determined by body weight (BW), but varies considerably amongst

individuals even between patients who bear the same body weight (BW). (Bergmann et al., 2014).

According to Kumar et al (2012) people with knee OA are believed to walk with high loads at the knee which are yet to be quantified using modelling techniques that account for subject specific electromyography (EMG) patterns, kinematics and kinetics.

Some investigators had attempted to estimate forces around the knee during various activities. Several approaches such as inverse dynamics, forward dynamics, and static body analyses had been used to relate knee kinematics and external forces to internal joint contact forces (Nisell, et al., 1999; Kaufman, et al., 1991; Wilk, et al., 1996; Shelburne & Pandy, 2002). Thus, it would be intriguing to determine the effect of loading at the lateral compartment of the knee joint (knock-knee) and the occupational relationship of some Ghanaian women.

1.5 Significance of the research

Based on the objective of the study, knowing the load acting on the lateral compartment of the knee joint would help predict which subject is more vulnerable to the deformity based on the occupation that they do. Knowing the load would be very relevant for improving joint replacement, physiotherapy, biomechanical computer simulation, surgical procedures, and in the advice to give to patients with osteoarthritis about what activities to avoid. Having knowledge of contact forces acting in the lateral compartment joints is a key determinant for testing fatigue, wear, or strength of implants, for analyses of strain distribution and remodelling at the fixation area and for other purposes.

Some research activities had been carried-out in the developed countries concerning osteoarthritis (Tang, et al., 2015; Brouwer, et al., 2007; Felson D. T., 2003; (Dillon, et al. 2006). Bold and innovative actions had been taken in order to minimize the burden brought about this ever-growing public health issue. However, in Ghana, no needed research activity had been

done so far to estimate risk factors associated with the disease, and provide strategies and interventions in management of the disease in Ghana.

Thus, this study would serve as the baseline data towards this disease and would provide important and valuable information to healthcare practitioners in Ghana.

1.6 General Objective

The goal of the study was to determine the occupational relationship of women and the effect of loading on the lateral compartment of the knee joints as is the case with valgus knee deformity.

1.6.1 Specific objectives

1. Determine the relationship between valgus knee deformity (knock-knee) and each of the variables; age, weight, and levels of malalignment.

1.7 Limitations of study

In the study, even though the tibiofemoral angle (TBF) and mechanical angle deviation (MAD) were measured to the nearest 1 degree, the head of the femur and the talus of the tibia were not visible from the full-limb radiographic images obtained. Hence there could be minimal errors in the measurement. Information on occupational history of all subjects and their occupational exposures were not obtained hence predictions on the effect of loading on the lateral compartment of the knee joints in relation to the various occupation were based on assumptions. Heights of the subjects were assumed using their respective weights in reference from literatures.

1.8 Organisation of thesis

This study is organised under six main chapters. The first chapter comprises of the background of the study, the problem statement, and justification of the study, objectives, significance of the study, and limitation and organisation of thesis. The second chapter contains details of the review of literatures related to the study. The third chapter is devoted to the research methodology. In this chapter, the study design, population, measurement of images, and ethical consideration were outlined. Chapter four contains theoretical method used for the study. Results and discussions are found in chapter five and, finally, chapter six contains conclusion and recommendation.

CHAPTER 2

LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Introduction

This chapter takes into account other works in line with this study. General overview of literature related to osteoarthritis. This includes; definition of key terms, prevalence, risk factors, symptoms, diagnoses, laboratory test, pharmacological treatments, non-pharmacological treatments, medication, and management of osteoarthritis.

2.2 Definition of osteoarthritis

Osteoarthritis can be explained from a pathological, radiographic or clinical perspective. The radiographic perspective provides the best media in ascertaining the presence and extremity of osteoarthritis due to its ease of standardization as well as acquisition. This is done by means of the Kellgren and Lawrence (Kl) grading system. The system grades the severity of osteoarthritis using five grades, from zero (0) to four (4). This system of classification was proposed by Kellgren and Lawrence in 1957 and later credited by World Health and Organization (WHO) in 1961. Grade zero (0) implies the absence of radiographic signs of OA, grade one (1) indicates a probable joint space narrowing (JSN) and likely, osteophytic lipping. Grade two (2) indicates absolute presence of osteophytes and JSN on anterior posterior load compounding radiograph. Grade three (3) implies that various osteophytes are present with JSN, sclerosis as well as the possibility of bony deformity. The next grade, that is, grade four (4) shows huge osteophytes, visible JSN, worsen sclerosis and bony deformity. (Kellgreen & Lawrence, 1957). This system of grading system had been mostly applied in hand and hip osteoarthritis. For the knee, however, it was used to determine tibiofemoral osteoarthritis with the clear radiographic features of X-rays indicating osteoarthritis of the patellofemoral joint. Presently, no generally approved magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) definition of osteoarthritis had been reached although a basic definition circling around the cartilage lesions,

osteophytes, bone marrow lesions (BMLs), synovitis and effusion had been used as a guide. (Johnson & Hunter, 2014)

2.3 Incidence and prevalence of osteoarthritis

There is limited literature on the incidence and prevalence of osteoarthritis. This is because, there is no specific solution to determine its onset. (Pfleger & Woolf, 2003). Although there are a number of studies with varying predictions on the degrees of osteoarthritis occurrence and existence, there is a general consensus that the most susceptible class to osteoarthritis are adults. This is clearly shown in fig 2.1. (Allen & Golightly, 2015). A reliable data was by the National Arthritis Data Workgroup (NADW) in 2005 which predicted that, 27 million U.S. citizens aged eighteen (18) years or more had the clinical type of osteoarthritis. The Framingham Osteoarthritis Cohort had one of the best-known information about the existence of symptomatic osteoarthritis. NADW relied on the prevalence estimate proposed by the Framingham osteoarthritis cohort and predicted that 6.8 percent of people aged twenty-six (26) years and above showed signs of symptomatic osteoarthritis of the hand of which age-standardized rate were 3.8 percent for men and 9.2 percent for women. On the bases of the estimations arrived by NADW, they concluded that 13 million U.S. aged twenty-six (26) years and above had symptomatic hand osteoarthritis. The NADW also estimated in 2005 that 9.3 million (4.9 percent) U.S. of adults who were at least twenty-six (26) years old had symptomatic knee osteoarthritis and 6.7 percent of the people aged forty-five (45) years and beyond suffered symptomatic hip osteoarthritis. (Murphy & Helmick, 2012). Similar studies from Australia also showed that osteoarthritis was most prevalent amongst women (2.95 percent) than men (1.71 percent) per 1000 population among all age groups.

Globally, it had been predicted that 9.6 percent of men and eighteen (18) percent of women who were at least sixty (60) of age were affected by symptomatic osteoarthritis. (Pfleger & Woolf, 2003). A Swedish survey, reported that hip osteoarthritis is minimal, with radiographic

prevalence of 1.9 percent amongst men and 2.3 percent among women with age of forty-five (45) years and above. The prevalence in United Kingdom (UK) was estimated to be 12.5 percent. It was reported that the prevalence was about eight (8) percent to thirteen (13) percent in New Zealand, Belgium and the Netherlands. In developing countries, prevalence of osteoarthritis was confirmed to be relatively low and ranged between 2.3 percent to 11.3 percent. A study was done in rural Tswana population of Phokeng in South Africa which showed that prevalence of knee OA in Africa is 20238 for men and 30208 for women for every 100,000 each of men and women who were at least 35 years old. Also, hip osteoarthritis showed a 3278 prevalence rate in men and 725 in women who were aged fifty-five (55) years and above. From the above study, it was evident that hip osteoarthritis was common amongst men in the study area. (Naeem, 2014). According to Dr. Michael Ofori, an immunologist at the Noguchi Memorial Institute for Medical Research, Ghana, autoimmune diseases are experiencing a rise. This was said in a speech he made at the launch of ShareCare Ghana in 2008. (Naeem, 2014)

Figure 2. 1: Age and sex-specific incidence rates (/1000 person-years) of knee osteoarthritis (black), hip osteoarthritis (red), and hand osteoarthritis (green). All population; short dash line, women; long dash line, men (Alhambra, et al., 2014; Allen & Golightly, 2015).

2.4 Risk factors

Osteoarthritis is a multifactorial disease which borders on both system and local factors. For instance, an injury may set off the development of OA in an individual who may have been predisposed to its development by virtue of inheriting it at an early age. The significance of risk factors may be distinct for several joints, at different levels of the disease, considering each development stage as against the progression of disease as well as the radiographic and symptomatic disease. Some other findings had showed that, risk factors vary from one person to the other based on different radiographic characteristics like osteophytes and joint space narrowing. (Zhang & Jordan, 2010).

2.4.1 Person-level risk factors

Factors that constitute person-level risk factors and their associated evidences are considered under demographic characteristics, family history, obesity, genetics, gender and age, diet, bone density and mass, and race. (Allen & Golightly, 2015)

2.4.1.1 Demographic characteristics and family history

Quite a number of studies (Johnson & Hunter, 2014; Neogi & Zhang, 2013) (Neogi & Zhang, 2013) had proven women with increasing age had shown higher risk of osteoarthritis. Others had shown higher risks among people within the lower socioeconomic class, (Cleveland, et al., 2013; (Callahan, et al., 2011)), and African American origin (Dillon, et al, 2006; (Jordan, et al., 2007)). Some studies, (Pan, et al., 2014; (Khan, et al., 2014)) had also shown that people whose knees had undergone total knee replacement had higher knee pain prevalence and joint space narrowing with time.

2.4.1.2 Obesity

One of the global problems leading to excess morbidity and mortality is obesity. People who are overweight are more prone to knee OA. It had been realised that the effect of obesity on osteoarthritis cannot be overruled because it had become a fast growing and dangerous public health problem. World Health Organization (WHO) had reported that over 1.6 billion adults who are 51 years and beyond are obese (WHO, report). This had aroused several interest from people to look into the relationship between obesity and OA taking into account its modifiable status. Very significant evidences attest to the fact that obesity stands as one of the most alarming risk factors for OA at peripheral joints, especially at the knee and hip region. (Jiang, et al., 2011). Thus more individuals who are obese are likely to be affected by knee OA in the future (Johnson & Hunter, 2014).

Although obesity does characterize the growth of OA, it also increases the possibility of radiographic progression. (Johnson & Hunter, 2014). A recent review revealed a dose-response relationship between obesity and the risk of knee OA; with a 35 percent risk of being affected by knee OA for every 5-unit rise in the body mass index (BMI) of an individual. In a study on the Swedish population, (Lohmander, et al., 2009) found knee OA susceptibility to be 8.1 for subjects with BMI greater than 30 kgm^{-2} . The Framingham cohort study showed that a weight drop of 5 kg gives a 50 percent chance of a minimal risk in the development of knee OA (Felson, et al. 1992). Another study showed that the influence of obesity on a population with the risk of attracting knee OA was 29 percent and the percentage increases with increasing prevalence of obesity (Zhang W. , 2010). Nonetheless, this relation exists more with respect to hip OA than knee OA. Hand OA also had a correlation with obesity, that is, radiographic and incident symptomatic hand OA. (Johnson & Hunter, 2014).

2.4.1.3 Genetics

Several studies had shown that genes also contribute to OA pathophysiologic pathways and the risk of OA. Different forms of osteoarthritis appears to be genetically determined with at least 50 percent of the cases being osteoarthritis in the hands, hips (Felson, et al., 2000) and 40 % being knee OA (Johnson & Hunter, 2014). Genes for vitamin D receptors, insulin-like growth factor 1, type 2 collagen and growth differentiation factor 5 (GDF5) may provide targets for future pharmaceutical approaches. (Johnson & Hunter, 2014). According to Kerkhof et al, (2010) in their genome-wide association study, the C allele of rs3815148 on chromosome 7q22 was associated with a 1.14-fold increased prevalence of knee and or hand OA, and also with a 30% increased risk of knee OA progression. (Kerkhof, et al., 2010). Many studies had indicated an indirect relation between the hypermobility of the general joint, a lone benign trait, with respect to hand and knee OA, and serum cartilage oligometric matrix protein levels. (Zhang & Jordan, 2010).

2.4.1.4 Gender and age

Age stands out as one of the most causative factors of OA, however the relation between age and the prevalence of OA had been misconstrued. The rise in OA with age as a contributing factor may be as a result of the biological transformation that occurs with aging hence making the joints less capable of coping with adverse conditions such as cartilage thinning, weak muscle, poor proprioception, and oxidative damage. (Zhang & Jordan, 2010).

Women largely suffer from OA of the hand, foot and knee OA than men (Srikanth, et al., 2005). The definite increase in menopause in women had led to theories relating the role of oestrogen in OA. Symptoms of OA may be unmasked by oestrogen by excruciating pain sensitivity; but, findings from observational studies and clinical trials had yielded conflicting results (Hanna, et al., 2004; (Nevitt, et al., 2001)). Differences in gender may also be as a result of varying bone strength, alignment, ligament laxity, pregnancy and neuromuscular strength. Females may experience a reduced amount of knee cartilage than men, but it is still unclear if had a relation with accelerated cartilage loss. (Johnson & Hunter, 2014).

2.4.1.5 Diet

Diet is one of the considerable subjects of interest regarding OA, however, results from several findings had been conflicting. Evidence indicates that reactive oxygen species can accumulate with age and can be developed in joints, destroying articular tissues. In addition, studies conducted on animals had shown that early life nutrition also contributes to OA, but this is not same in humans (McAlindon, et al., 1996). One of the causative nutritional factors for OA is Vitamin D. Deficiency or lack of vitamin D can result in bones becoming thin, brittle or misshapen. (Zhang & Jordan, 2010). The Framingham study revealed that people within the lowest (<27 ng/mL) and mid portions (27.0–33.0 ng/mL) of tertile serum 25-hydroxy vitamin D showed a three times higher rate of risk for the progression of knee OA as against those in

the highest tertile, but none of these effects were seen for risk of onset of the disease. (Felson, et al., 2000).

In the studies conducted by (Mcalindon, et al., 1996), they found that antioxidant vitamins also contribute to OA. Smaller quantum of vitamin C had been tagged with a high risk of the progression of OA in the knee, whereas higher amount of vitamin C in the system had showed reduction in radiographic knee OA likewise the risk of experiencing increasing pains in the knee.

One of the important regulators of bone and cartilage mineralization is vitamin K. Low amount of plasma phylloquinone (<0.5 nmoles/l) had an increasing influence on the prevalence ratios for OA, joint space narrowing and osteophytes in the hand, and osteophytes in the knee. (Neogi, et al., 2006)

No substantial claims had been made regarding the possibility of a high intake of any of the antioxidant nutrients minimizing the occurrence of knee OA or the volume of cartilage. Thus, future investigations should be done in order to ascertain the link between OA and dietary factors. (Johnson & Hunter, 2014).

2.4.1.6 Bone density and bone mass

Previous studies had pointed out that increased bone density creates the risk for occurrence of OA, but its direct operational and casual relation remains unclear (Neogi & Zhang, 2013). Other two studies (Hardcastle, et al., 2014; (Hardcastle, et al., 2015)) had showed that people with high bone masses stand a higher risk of suffering radiographic hip and knee osteoarthritis than people with normal bone mass. High bone mass generates subchondral bone sclerosis thereby leading to the formation of hypertrophic OA phenotype. This goes a long way to confirm the role of high bone mass in the development of OA since it is characterized by a lifelong genetic trait. (Allen & Golightly, 2015).

2.4.1.7 Race/Ethnicity

Studies had shown that OA and its associated challenges, and patterns of joints affected by OA differ from ethnic or racial group to the other. (Zhang & Jordan, 2010). A comparative study on Osteoarthritis between the Framingham and the Chinese in Beijing was done and it resulted that hip and hand OA were less prevalent among the Chinese. However, Chinese women in Beijing showed a high prevalence rate of both symptomatic and radiographic knee OA than the white women in the Framingham Study. (Zhang, et al., 2001). Also, results from the Johnson Country OA Project showed almost the same prevalence levels of OA of the hip in African American women (23%) and white women (22%), but this was not the same for men belonging to the African American race which showed higher prevalence rate of 21 percent than a rate of 17 percent for white men. African Americans were at a higher risk of having severer conditions of tri-compartmental osteophytes than the whites, (Nelson, et al., 2010).

2.4.2 Joint-level risk factors

Risk factors that threatens joints of individuals and their visible relation with the start and progression of OA are injury/surgery, alignment, physical activities, and occupation.

2.4.2.1 Injury/Surgery

A number of studies had showed that injury to the knee makes the knee prone to OA. OA development and musculoskeletal symptomatology can occur as a result of serious injury to the joint, particularly a trans-articular fracture or meniscal tear (Lohmander, et al., 2004; (Roos, et al., 2001)). The Framingham Study showed that subjects with radiographic knee OA face greater chances of meniscal damage than those without OA. Meniscal damage increases with a rise in the K/L grade ($p < 0.001$ for trend), that is, those with K/L of 3 and 4, representing moderate and severe levels radiographic knee OA respectively, showed visible signs of meniscal damage (Englund, et al., 2008).

2.4.2.2 Alignment

The hip-knee-ankle angle (i.e., the knee alignment) is one of the key factors of load distribution. (Cerejo, et al., 2002). A deviation from the normal alignment of the hip, knee, affects the load distributed at the knee. Maligned knees are more susceptible to OA with higher chances of the disease developing at a higher rate than knees with normal alignment. (Zhang & Jordan, 2010). It was demonstrated in a study that knees already affected with OA, showed greater abnormal anatomic alignment coupled with accelerated structural deterioration in the compartment under greatest compressive stress. (Sharma, et al, 2001). OA knees plus varus alignment at the baseline was associated with a four times increase in the risk of suffering a progression of knee osteoarthritis at the medial level, and those with valgus alignment at baseline had a nearly five times increase in the risk of lateral progression. The study further revealed the influence of varus or valgus malalignment on the rate of progression of OA. The malalignment was more evident in knees with severe baseline radiographic disease than knees with moderate disease. (Cerejo, et al., 2002). Bone marrow lesions and rapid cartilage loss also had a correlation with knee malalignment. However, it is still unclear how malalignment can be linked with the chances of suffering OA. In a Rotterdam research study, normal, valgus and varus alignments were juxtaposed and it was observed that varus alignment had a two times increase rate of OA development than valgus alignment with a normal alignment showing no possible signs of OA development (Brouwer, et al., 2007). (Hunter, et al., 2007) in the Framingham Study used four knee alignment indicators, that is, condylar angle, anatomic axis, tibia plateau angle, and condylar tibia plateau angle, and found that none of these indicators had no bearings with a possible increase in the risk of incident radiographic knee OA.

2.4.2.3 Physical activities/sports

Physical activities or sports also had a role to play in the onset and progression of OA in the knee. Conflicting results had emerged from various studies on the link between sporting activities and the incidence of OA. A comparison study between non-soccer playing athletes and elite soccer players proved that those with a higher chance of getting knee OA are elite soccer players. Also, long distance runners had a high risk of developing hip and knee OA. Generally, the intensity of physical activity may also contribute a high risk of OA. It was discovered in the Framingham study that the common physical activity engaged in by the aged was leisure-time walking and sometimes, gardening but others who engaged in high intensity physical activities were exposed to greater risk of suffering from radiographic knee OA (McAlindon, et al., 1999). In another study, women who were involved in regular high intensity physical activities showed greater chances of being exposed to hip OA (Lane, et al., 1999).

2.4.2.4 Occupation

When a particular joint is used frequently during work, it stands a greater chance of being affected by OA. It had been seen in some studies that people whose jobs involve squatting or kneeling, or lifting of heavy weights, especially those who are overweight, are two times likely to develop knee OA than jobs that do not demand such physical activities. (Johnson & Hunter, 2014). OA of the hip is mostly as a result of prolonged standing and lifting of weights. Features of hand OA had been identified with occupation that require increased dexterity. Evidence had emerged that one such occupation as farming, had a high prevalence of hip OA. (Croft, et al, 1992). In fig. 2.2, occupations that demand repeated pincer grip suffered more OA at distal interphalangeal joints than those that required power grip. (Zhang & Jordan, 2010).

Figure 2. 2: Pathogenesis of OA with putative risk factors. (Zhang & Jordan, 2010).

2.5 Symptoms of osteoarthritis

The basic symptom that is experienced or observed among people suffering from OA is pain at the affected joints. The pain is mostly excruciating during the day. Other symptoms include creaking, warmth and swelling of the joint. There can also be occurrence of stiffness of the joints after prolong hours of inactiveness. With severe cases of OA, complete loss of cartilage brings about friction in the bones resulting in pain either at rest or with the slightest motion embarked on.

OA symptoms differ largely based on the individual patient. Some of the patients can become weakened based on their symptoms. Others may experience a few remarkable signs of dramatic degeneration of the joints. Also, OA symptoms may be occasional.

Though in theory osteoarthritis can affect any joint in the body, it can also affect the feet, hands, spine, and large weight-bearing joints, such as the hips and knees. Progression of OA can typically affect movement patterns such as gait.

Generally, OA of the knee can result from obesity or any history of repetitive injury and/or surgery the knee joint. In extreme cases, cartilage degeneration at the knee joints may result in outward curvature of the knee called Varus (“bow leg”) or inward curvature known as Valgus (“knock-knee”). Limping may also set in and this can be aggravated by further cartilage degeneration. Sometimes the pain, limping or general joint dysfunction experienced by some of the patients may show resistance to medications or other conservative measures. In the United States, extreme OA of the knee easily leads calls for total knee replacement (TKR) surgical procedures.

2.6 Diagnosis

The aetiology of OA is multifactorial. Early realization of patients having OA of the knee and the correction of its associated risk factors is very crucial. Diagnosis can be confirmed base on the history and clinical or radiological features. Depending on the patients especially those having suspected clinical features, recognition of the disease or deciding the degree of joint association may require performance of radiography or MRI examinations. According to the American College of Rheumatology, diagnosing pain in the knee can be done using the history and clinical examination, history and clinical examination plus radiological findings, and history and clinical examination with laboratory findings of the patient (Behzad, 2011). Each criterion is used in conjunction with various key indicators in order to ascertain pain in the knee. For history and clinical examination findings, three of the following indicators can be used: age of 50 years and above, morning stiffness of at most 30 minutes, crepitus on active motions, bony tenderness, bony enlargement, and the absence of palpable warmth of synovium. When taking into account the history and clinical examination plus the radiographic findings of the patient, age of 50 years and beyond, morning stiffness below 30 minutes, crepitus on active motions and osteophyte can be used as an auxiliary factor in diagnosing pain in the knee. Also, a combination of any five of these; age more than 50 years, stiffness in the morning of at

most 30 minutes, crepitus on active motions, bony enlargement, no palpable warmth of synovium 6-ESR <40 mm/h, Rheumatoid Factor <1/40, and synovial fluid signs of osteoarthritis can be used in conjunction with the history and clinical examination, and the laboratory findings to diagnosis pain in the knee of the patient.

After a definite diagnosis is made, no additional examinations with regards to laboratory test are required. However, in more serious cases, tests such as complete blood test (CBC), Erythrocyte Sedimentation Rate (ESR) and C - reactive protein (CRP), and uric acid may provide additional diagnostic features as well as the performance of X-rays of the affected joints especially following trauma, which become helpful for reaching a definite diagnosis. (Behzad, 2011)

2.7 Treatment

The ultimate goal for treating OA in the knee is to do away with pain and inflammation, reduce the progression of the disease and improve or maintain mobility functions which include activities of daily living (ADLs), and health-related quality of life (HRQoL). (Newberry, et al., 2015). Treatment is determined by the medical history, overall health and age of the patient, the extent of condition, therapies, procedures and tolerance of the patient's body to specific medications, expectation for the course of the condition, patient's opinion or preference. If condition is reported early by patients, enough diagnosis and treatment can be done to prevent joint damage and impairment which sometimes occur at the early stages of the disease. (Naeem, 2014). The relative moderate progression of the disease takes into consideration a stepwise algorithmic way to deal with treatment. Based on systemic considerations of research evidence and expert consensus, the EULAR task force for osteoarthritis had come out with evidence-based recommendations for the treatment of knee OA. This include both surgical and non-surgical strategies. (Hussain, et al, 2016).

2.7.1 Non-surgical treatment

Four intervention strategies for non-surgical option include physical activity, self-management education, injury prevention and weight management, and healthy nutrition. (Giles & Klippel, 2010). Self-management education and physical activity primarily aims at minimizing the signs and later development of OA for patients having the disease. Injury and weight management provides opportunities for preventing the onset of the disease.

2.7.1.1 Self-management education (SME)

Self-management (SME) is a procedure that assists adults with worsen conditions of OA to adopt the most effective method to deal with their conditions, keep its short and long term well-being outcomes and accomplish the most ideal personal satisfaction. This had been used effectively with various chronic diseases, such as diabetes and asthma, and may be adopted in a number of settings such as community gathering places, the home, recreational camps, worksites and schools. SME can be an ideal public health intervention for OA as well. Though the impact of SME on individual pain and disability are small, these impacts translate into significant improvements when administered over a long period of time. Additionally, with relatively small financial investments, SME can give significant mental health and psychological results such as reduced forms of anxiety, depression and general health stress. These advantages coupled with the absence of side effects make SME a significant general well-being strategy and a helpful subordinate for the care administered in any clinical environment. (Giles & Klippel, 2010).

2.7.1.2 Physical activity

Physical activities had been shown by researchers that it reduces pain, enhances normal function and minimizes disabilities related to all forms of arthritis. Owing to the fact that overweight and obesity are known risk factors for OA, regular physical activities can help people achieve or maintain a healthy weight. The most secure and effective physical exercise

for adults with OA of the hip and knee are low-impact, moderate intensity aerobics such as walking, water exercise and cycling, and muscle strengthening exercises that use different forms of resistance. In patients having patellofemoral OA, physical activities such as stair climbing and squatting should be limited. Little investments of physical activities, for instance 60 minutes of physical activities per week can yield some improvements for OA patients but a 2.5 hour of moderate intensity aerobic and two days of muscle strengthening exercise per week is recommended to improve OA pain and function, and to assist with the prevention and management of other chronic conditions. In all, patients with OA should desist from being inactivity and be encouraged to engage in any physical activity that their abilities and conditions will allow. (Giles & Klippel, 2010).

2.7.1.3 Injury prevention

Prevention of injury is very vital for elderly patients who already had OA because they may be at greater risk of falling and sustaining injuries as a result of muscular weakness, impaired balance and gait dysfunction. Balance training and other forms of dynamic exercise had been shown to reduce the frequency and rate of falling amongst adults and are important components of a comprehensive physical activity program for adults. (Giles & Klippel, 2010).

2.7.1.4 Weight management and health nutrition

Research on the hazards of obesity continues to be alarming. Higher body mass index (BMI) had been cited as a potential cause of OA, especially that of the knee. Being overweight can increase pressure on weight bearing joints which eventually causes higher pain and inflammation involved with OA. Thus individuals who ensure normal and healthy weight had no chances of developing symptomatic knee OA as they age and in no way need any major surgical procedures to deal with OA symptoms. Nutritional factors also play a major role in the development, advancement and management of OA thus patients suffering from OA can adopt modern, quality and healthy dietary recommendations.

2.7.2 Orthoses and footwear

Orthoses and footwear help to limit pain and improve function. Patients with passively correctable uni-compartmental arthritis are the ideal candidate for orthosis. A brace may work by enhancing the bio-mechanical axis of the deformity thereby reducing or taking away the load on the compartment or by enhancing the view of instability as shown in fig. 2.3. Scientific evidence had showed that there is massive reduction in pain and improvement of function following the use of orthoses. (Hussain,et al, 2016)

Figure 2. 3: An off-loader brace that helps to re-align a correctable deformity. (Hussain et al, 2016).

2.7.3 Pharmacotherapy

Different types of medications had been utilized to control arthritis symptoms, prevent joint distortion and enhance mobility and function. There are five groups of arthritis medication; Non-Steroid Anti-Inflammatory Drugs (NSAIDs), analgesics (Painkillers), Intra-articular corticosteroids, Disease Modifying Anti-Rheumatic Drugs (DMARDs), and the recent biologics. Non-steroid anti-inflammatory drugs (NSAIDS) are recommended to the patients

when they present exacerbation of pain and swollen knee. These drugs work by blocking the proinflammatory agents as prostaglandins and leukotrienes by reversibly blocking the cyclooxygenase and lipoxygenase pathway. (Hussain, et al, 2016). Analgesics function by relieving pain. The relief induced by analgesics works by either blocking the pain signals moving to the brain or by interfering with the brain's interpretation of signals without causing loss of consciousness. Intra-articular corticosteroids are prescribed when there is exacerbation of symptoms despite using NSAIDS. They are very effective in controlling pain in OA, but the effect last approximately one week. Disease modifying anti-rheumatic drugs (DMARDs) slows the progress of the disease by modifying the immune systems. Biologics or biologic response modifiers help to stimulate or restore the immune system to fight the disease or infection. For instance, TNF-alpha fights inflammatory reactions. When anti-TNF drugs are applied, it is bonded to TNF-alpha, thereby making it inactive and unable to interfere with inflammatory activity and thus decreasing joint damage. (Naeem, 2014).

2.8 Surgical treatment

Surgical treatment option can be broadly classified as joint preserving and joint-replacing procedures.

2.8.1 Corrective osteotomy

Osteotomy is a surgical treatment that is used to shift the mechanical axis from the pathological area to the normal compartment. Different types of osteotomy had been described and these include closing-wedge, oblique plane osteotomy, opening wedge, and ball and socket osteotomy. But, the closed wedge and opening osteotomies had gained popularity due to their technical ease of utilization. For valgus knee deformity, corrective osteotomy is performed either by the supracondylar femoral or high tibia osteotomy based on the area and severity of the deformity. A lot of instruments had been brought-in for fixation of the bone osteotomy. In the past years, locking plates were manufactured to correct the problem of a possible cortex

breakage. But due to high cost of locking compression plates (LCPs), angle blade plates (ABPs) are commonly used. (Kazemi, et al., 2015)

No matter the type of osteotomy, the overall aim is to normalise the mechanical axis and off-load the distorted side. (Hussain,et al, 2016).

2.8.2 Partial or total knee replacement

Total knee replacement (TKR) is a surgical means by which the articular surfaces of the knee, the femoral condyles and tibia plateau are changed. It is usually reserved as the final option for patients with severe knee arthritis. With TKR, there is at least one plastic piece with a metal stem that is placed between the tibia and the femur, as a shock absorber. In almost 50 percent of the cases, the patella is also replaced owing to the reasons such as osteolysis, mal-tracking of the patella or failure of the implant. The goal of the patella reconstruction is to restore the extensor mechanism which depends on the level of bone loss and which kind of patella prosthesis is placed. The overall aim of TKR is to reduce individual pains and increase function. For the past decade, with advances in the implant design, better plastic wear properties and appropriate patient selection, 96 percent reproducible results had been achieved in one large American Cohort study. (Hussain, et al, 2016). Approximately 12-20 percent of people continue with at least moderate pain following surgery. The balance of risks and benefits of knee and hip replacement are similar. (Martin, 2005).

2.8.3 Natural remedies (herbal medicine)

One other alternative treatment of arthritis that is gaining popularity and complement traditional (clinical) therapies is herbal medicine. However, more scientific research is required to establish the claim of its effectiveness. Each of these medication options had serious side effects which should be discussed sufficiently with the patient so that he or she can effectively weigh the options and decide.

CHAPTER 3

THEORY

Gravitational force is the main force which acts on a body.

Let W = Weight and therefore;

$$W = mg \quad \text{Equation 1}$$

Where m = Mass (kg)

g = Gravity (ms^{-2})

The bone structure of the skeleton makes the body stable against the gravitational force.

Gravitational force (W) is depended on body mass distribution and is applied at the centre of gravity. For body stability, centre of gravity (CG) must be traced between the feet, and if the

feet are separated from each other, forces in horizontal direction F_x are considered as shown in

figure 3.1

$$\sum F_i = 0$$

Equation 2

Figure 3. 1: Indicating the weight exerted on both legs while standing

$$\vec{F}_1 + \vec{F}_2 = W \dots\dots\dots \text{Equation 3}$$

\vec{F}_1, \vec{F}_2 are the forces the ground applies to the feet.

Force F_1 is the ground reaction force. F_2 is the sum of the various forces of the rest of the body on the leg through the hip joint and surrounding muscles. F_3 is the gravitational pull of the earth downward on the leg. Force F_1 acts on the bottom of the leg, F_2 acts on the top, and F_3 acts somewhere in between. If the leg reaches equilibrium state, the addition of these forces must be equal to zero.

For instance, when a person is standing on both feet as shown in fig. 3.1, the earth pulls down at some point with force W . The floor pushes up on the right foot with force F_1 and on the left foot with force F_2 .

Translational equilibrium ignores points where forces within the body are applied. If rotational equilibrium is considered, fig. 3.1 had to be redrawn to show the points at which the various forces act on the person. If all the forces are vertical, then there is only one component of each force to consider, and the equilibrium condition gives

$$F_{1X} + F_{2X} - W = 0 \text{ or } F_1 + F_2 = W \dots\dots\dots \text{Equation 4}$$

If there is a sideway force on each foot, translational equilibrium provides two conditions:

$$F_{1X} + F_{2X} = 0 \text{ and } F_{1Y} + F_{2Y} - W = 0 \dots\dots\dots \text{Equation 5}$$

And if the person is standing with the same force on each foot, then

$$F_1 = F_2 = W/2 \dots\dots\dots \text{Equation 6}$$

Thus, based on the conditions of translational equilibrium, the component forces were determined and computed using java code.

CHAPTER 4

METHODOLOGY

4.0 Introduction

Methodology is a crucial part of every research and if the correct procedures for collection of data are not followed or are being compromised, the result will not be a true reflection of what is on the ground. This chapter focuses on how the data was collected for the research and the principles underlying the methods used.

4.1 Study setting

The study was carried-out at the St. John of God Hospital located at Duayaw Nkwanta, the District capital for the Tano North District in the Brong-Ahafo Region of Ghana. The current population of the district is estimated to be 74,775 people (St. John of God Hospital, Report, 2016). The St. John of God Hospital had an excellent Orthopaedic centre which offers best healthcare services to its clients and it is rated among the top three hospitals in Ghana. The primary focus of the hospital is to serve an ethnically diverse lower to middle-income population and, provide high quality primary and secondary levels of healthcare to patients (St. John of God Hospital, Report, 2016).

4.2 Study population

The study population comprised of 90 adult female patients (aged 40-83 years), who had presented cases with valgus knee deformity at the St. John of God Hospital from 2015-2018. Those below the age of 40 years were excluded from the study because OA had been shown to be relatively uncommon below that age. The study was also limited to valgus knee deformity (knock-knees) because it had been observed to be the most common deformity of the knee amongst Ghanaian elderly women (Private Communication, 2018). The goal of the study was to determine the effect of load distribution on the lateral compartment of the knee and the occupational relationship. Information on patients' age, weight, and occupation were obtained

based on the questionnaires administered directly to the patients. Patients' folders were reviewed from 2015 to 2018 and question used to determine the presence or absence of symptoms in the folders were, "had you ever had pain in or around a knee on most days for at least a month?" If the patients responded "yes", then a series of questions was administered inquiring further about the site of pain, its duration, the last time pain occurred, and its severity. Patients were characterized as having symptoms at the time of the examination if they stated that the pain had last occurred within the previous 2 or more years. Weight-bearing anterior-posterior (AP knee standing) and lateral knee radiographs of the patients were obtained and each of the radiographic images were analysed to determine the maligned angle. The occupation of the patients were put into four main groups (farming, trading, teaching, and others which comprises (civil servant, retired personnel, nurse, catering, and seamstress)). Using the mass (kg), information on patients' heights were obtained according to weight-watchers. The body mass index (BMI) of each patient was calculated as the ratio of the mass (kg) to the square of the height in meters. The mean and the standard error on age, BMI, and weight were calculated respectively. Statistical analysis was done by conditional regression for matched sets.

4.3 Radiographic measurements

Anterior posterior (A.P.) and lateral weight bearing radiographs of the lower limb was obtained on each patient. According to Sharma et al, 2001, the golden rule on measuring normal alignment of the knee is by drawing a line in an anterior posterior (A.P.) plane that begins at the centre of the femoral head, which passes through the centre of the knee, and continues to the centre of the ankle. This line represents the mechanical axis of the lower extremities. A second line was drawn to the centre of the tibial spine which established the mechanical axis of the tibia. Where the two lines intersected on the knee represented the mechanical axis deviation and was recorded to the nearest one degree as shown in figure 4.1. Valgus

malalignment is defined at a mechanical axis of 10° or more. For a severe valgus knee, the degree of angulation is greater than 15° .

Figure 4. 1: Mechanical axis of deviation of weight-bearing anterior posterior radiograph of valgus knee deformity measured at 45.1°

Similarly using the same full-length radiograph, the anatomic axis was measured based upon the methods of (Moreland, et al., 1987). The femoral anatomic axis was measured by extending a line from the shaft axis of the femur and extended through to the distal femur. A subsequent line was drawn from the centre of the tibial spine, midway between the medial and lateral surfaces. The angle of intersection of the axes formed on the knee known is as the tibiofemoral angle. This angle was recorded to the nearest one degree as shown in figure 4.2.

The mean angle and the standard deviation were calculated on both the mechanical angle of deviation and tibiofemoral angle.

Figure 4. 2: Anatomical tibiofemoral angle of weight-bearing anterior posterior radiograph of valgus knee deformity measured at 21.9°

4.4 Ethical considerations

Ethics in research are the acceptable ways to conduct research especially those with human subject. Departmental approval from the St. John of God Hospital's Orthopaedic Centre at Duayaw Nkwanta was sought. The principle of informed consent was fully adhered to. The information obtained on the patients were kept anonymous and treated with the utmost confidentiality it deserved. The study was conducted with due diligence to avoid any form of harm (both physical and social) to the patients.

CHAPTER 5

5.1 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The data presented were collected on ninety (90) patients. Forty-eight (48) of the patients had their right knees affected and the remaining forty-two (42) were affected on their left knees. The site of the defect is mostly due to the most exposed leg to the physical activities associated with the occupations of the subjects. Hence patients who engaged their right leg often had their right knee affected by the deformity, and vice versa. Eighty-five (85) of the patients were involved in occupation which were grouped into four (4); farming, trading, teaching, and others constituting catering, civil servant, nursing, seamstress, housewife, and a retired personnel as shown in table 5.1. Catering, civil servant, nursing, seamstress, housewife, and a retired personnel were classified as others because there were no much data on them. Six (6) of the subjects were unemployed and there were no records of employment on five (5) of them. All values of the shear force in x and y directions and the resultants force were determined. The resultants force calculated was equivalent to the weight with zero errors. The objective of the study was to determine the effect of force distribution at the lateral compartment of the knee joints in relation to occupation since it is the direction at which the knee was deformed, thus we considered the x-component shear force and plotted it against occupation.

The level of severity of the deformity in the subjects was determined by considering the normal valgus angle of 10 degrees and the mechanical angle of deviation. The difference between these two angles is what is associated to the degree of deformity. Thus the patients showed varying degrees of deformity based on the analysis showed in table 1 in appendix A. Though all the patients had been affected by the deformity, 41 percent of them showed higher levels of deformity while 59 percent showed minimal levels of the deformity when compared to the mean value.

The mean value and standard error for weight, age, tibiofemoral angle, mechanical angle deviation, the shear component force in x-direction and vertical directions and resultant force, were calculated respectively as shown in table 5.2. The graphical representation of the data was plotted for the various parameters as indicated in figures 5.1 to 5.7.

Table 5. 1: Occupation and corresponding number of patients.

Occupation	Number of patients
Farming	29
Trading	38
Teaching	5
Unemployment	6
No record of employment	5
Others (Civil servant (2), retiring, catering, nursing, housewife, seamstress)	7
Total	90

Table 5. 2: Data representing mean and standard error of the parameters used in the analysis

Variables	Mean and standard error
Age	56.24 ± 1.06
Weight	78.11 ± 1.82
Tibiofemoral angle	13.36 ± 0.71
Mechanical Angle of Deviation (MAD)	28.05 ± 0.95
x-component force (shear force)	8.71 ± 0.52
Height	1.76 ± 0.02
(BMI)	24.85 ± 0.09
Degree of deformity	18.05 ± 0.95

The shear force, the level of malalignment (tibiofemoral angle), the age and weight were illustrated in the figures 5.1 to 5.7.

Figure 5. 1: Tibiofemoral angle against shear force for farmers

From figure 5.1, there was an established relationship between the angle and the shear force. The lowest angle corresponded with the lowest shear force and the highest angle also corresponded with the highest shear force but not linearly related. The relationship appeared to follow a polynomial function. However, it could be seen that there existed some patients with the same angle of malalignment but different shear force.

Regression of the force component (fx) on the angle component (tibiofemoral angle) showed that the fx component is highly significant at a 1 percent level with a positive coefficient. This means that a percentage increase in the fx component would increase the angle component by

0.01 percent. Tables 5.3 and 5.4 gave clarification of the regression and descriptive analysis of the fx component and the tibiofemoral angle.

Table 5. 3: Regression analysis for farmers

Variables	Coefficient	Standard error	P-value
Fx-component	0.002	0.007	0.000
Intercept	4.859	1.545	0.000

Table 5. 4: Descriptive analysis for farmers

Variables	Mean	Standard error	Min	Max
Fx-component	8.71	0.58	4.91	19.24
Tibiofemoral angle	14.20	0.10	6.10	31.90

From table 5.4 above, it was evident that the mean value for the fx-component is 8.71 ± 0.58 N and the mean value for the angle was 14.20 ± 0.10 degree. The least and the highest shear force were 4.90 and 19.24 N respectively. In comparing the least and highest shear force to the mean value, the least shear force (4.90 N) was within range and the highest value (19.24 N) indicated an extreme case. Similarly, the least and highest maligned angle are 6.10 and 31.90 degrees respectively. When they were compared to the mean angle, the least value was within range and the highest value depicted an extreme case.

Figure 5. 2: Tibiofemoral angle against force for traders.

From figure 5.2, there was a correlation between the tibiofemoral angle and the shear force but the relationship appeared to follow an exponential and linear function. Here, it could be seen that the degree of deformity increased as the shear force increased. However, there were exceptional cases where patients with the same angle had different shear force.

Regression of the force component (fx) on the angle component (tibiofemoral angle), revealed that the fx component was highly significant at a 1 percent level with a positive coefficient. This explained the fact that a percentage increase in the shear force increased the maligned angle by 0.003 percent. Tables 5.5 and 5.6 gave clarification of the regression and descriptive analysis of the fx component and the tibiofemoral angle.

Table 5. 5: Regression analysis for traders

Variables	Coefficient	Standard error	P-value
Fx-component	0.003	0.007	0.000
Intercept	1.090	1.223	0.000

Table 5. 6: Descriptive analysis for traders

Variables	Mean	Standard error	Min	Max
Fx-component	8.44	0.72	3.91	23.18
Tibiofemoral angle	12.25	1.00	5.60	30.90

From table 5.6 above, the mean shear force was 8.44 ± 0.72 N and corresponding minimum and maximum values of 3.91 and 23.18 N respectively. The tibiofemoral angle had a mean value of 12.25 ± 1.00 degree and corresponding minimum and maximum values of 5.60 and 30.90 degrees respectively. When the minimum and maximum values of the shear force were compared to the mean shear force, it demonstrated that the minimum value (3.91 N) was within range and the maximum value (23.18 N) indicated an extreme case. Similarly, the minimum and maximum angle were compared to the mean angle, and it was clear that the minimum value (5.60 degree) was within range and the maximum value (30.90 degree) depicted an extreme case.

Figure 5. 3: Tibiofemoral angle against force for teachers.

Figure 5.3 showed a clear association between the shear force and the level of malalignment and the relationship appeared to follow an exponential function. The lowest shear force corresponded with the lowest angle and the highest force corresponded with the highest angle. However, there existed a patient with a low shear force but high level of malalignment.

Regression analysis of the force component (fx) on the angle component (tibiofemoral angle), revealed that the fx component was highly significant at the percent level with a positive coefficient. This means that a percentage increase in the force caused an increase in the angle by 1.044 percent. Tables 5.6 and 5.7 gave clarification of the regression and descriptive analysis of the fx component and the tibiofemoral angle.

Table 5. 7: Regression analysis for teachers

Variables	Coefficient	Standard error	P-value
Fx-component	1.044	0.023	0.017
Intercept	-2.828	3.630	0.017

Table 5. 8: Descriptive analysis for teachers

Variables	Mean	Standard error	Min	Max
Fx-component	5.67	1.13	3.65	15.61
Tibiofemoral angle	8.18	1.64	6.80	23.7

From table 5.8 above, the average shear force was 5.67 ± 1.13 N and corresponding minimum and maximum values of 3.65 and 15.61 N respectively. The tibiofemoral angle had an average value of 8.18 ± 1.64 degree and corresponding minimum and maximum values of 6.80 and 23.7 degrees respectively. When the mean shear force was compared to the minimum and maximum values, it showed that the minimum value (3.65 N) was within range and the maximum value (15.61) demonstrated an extreme case. Similarly, the minimum and maximum angles were compared to the average angle and it depicted that minimum angle (6.80 degree) was within range and maximum angle (23.7) indicated an extreme case.

Figure 5. 4: Tibiofemoral angle against force for others

From figure 5.4, there was an established connection between the angle and the shear force. The lowest angle corresponded with the lowest shear force and the highest angle also corresponded with the highest shear force but not linearly related. The relationship appeared to follow a polynomial function.

Regression analysis of the force component (fx) on the angle component (tibiofemoral angle) revealed that the fx component was highly significant at the 1 percent level with a positive coefficient. This means that a percentage increase in the force would cause an increase in the angle by 0.008 percent. Tables 5.9 and 5.10 gave clarification of the regression and descriptive analysis of the fx component and the tibiofemoral angle.

Table 5. 9: Regression analysis for others

Variables	Coefficient	Standard error	P-value
Fx-component	0.008	0.021	0.081
Intercept	3.795	6.118	0.081

Table 5. 10: Descriptive analysis for others

Variables	Mean	Standard error	Min	Max
Fx-component	11.81	2.35	5.61	21.16
Tibiofemoral angle	16.71	3.65	7.50	33.1

From table 5.10 above, the average shear force was 11.81 ± 2.35 N and corresponding minimum and maximum values of 5.61 and 21.16 N respectively. The tibiofemoral angle had an average value of 16.71 ± 1.64 degree and corresponding minimum and maximum values of 7.50 and 33.1 degrees respectively. When the mean shear force was compared to the minimum and maximum values, it showed that the minimum value (3.65 N) was within range and the maximum value (15.61) showed an extreme case. Similarly, the minimum and maximum angles were compared to the average angle and it depicted that minimum angle (6.80 degree) was within range and maximum angle (23.7) demonstrated an extreme case.

Figure 5. 5: Group of occupation against weighted average force

From figure 5.5, it was obvious that teachers showed the least value of average shear force and traders demonstrated a high average shear force. However, it could be deduced that all patients were involved in strenuous occupation. Strenuous occupation is a job which is entailed with specific physical activities such; squatting, kneeling, stair-climbing, heavy lifting, walking, standing, sitting, and driving. (Croft et al, 1992). In this finding, it was clear that all the occupation listed were somehow demanding with the aforementioned physical activities. Patients who demonstrated increased shear force on the lateral compartment of their knee joints were assumed to be exposed to specific physical activities which were held for a longer period of time. When engaged in such activities in one way or the other for a longer duration, a repetitive stress was being placed on the knee joint which caused more load to be exerted, thereby resulting in the progression of the disease.

Also this study attested with two most population based surveys in the USA, where they found that knee osteoarthritis was linked to occupational kneeling and squatting. (Anderson & Felson, 1988). In their analysis of cross sectional data from the first national Health and Nutrition Examination Survey (HANES 1) study, they found that radiographic osteoarthritis of the knee at ages fifty-five (55) to sixty-four (64) years was three times more common in persons whose jobs were seen to be likely involved with knee bending. (Anderson & Felson, 1988). Furthermore, a follow up study was made on 1400 men and women from the Framingham study and radiographic knee osteoarthritis was seen to be higher in people whose occupations were classified as both physically demanding and entailed knee bending (Felson, et al., 1991).

Figure 5. 6: Tibiofemoral angle against age

From figure 5.6 above, it was evident that there was no established correlation between age and the degree of malalignment. As the age increased, the degree of malalignment decreased.

Table 5.11 below gave a clarification of the regression analysis of the maligned angle and the age.

Table 5. 11: Regression analysis for farmers

Variables	Coefficient	Standard error	P-value
Tibiofemoral angle	0.005	0.003	0.3008
Intercept	23.365	12.569	0.3008

According to Zang et al (2010), age in relation to the development and rise in the prevalence of osteoarthritis was defined as a consequence cumulative exposure to various risk factors, and biologic changes that occurred with aging that may make a joint less able to cope with adversity, such as cartilage thinning, weak muscle strength, poor proprioception, and oxidative damage.

Thus in this study, age was not considered as a factor because all the patients showed varying degree of deformity irrespective of the age. Hence, there could be other factors that are playing active role in making the patients prone to the deformity.

Figure 5. 7: Tibiofemoral angle against weight

From figure 5.7, it was evident that there was no link between the weight and the angle. Each patient depicted different level of malalignment with the respective weight although there existed some patients with the same weight. A greater percentage of the patients showed optimum level of severity of the deformity as evident in their angles of deviation of the knee.

Table 5.12 below gave a clarification of the regression analysis of the weight and the tibiofemoral angle.

Table 5. 12: Regression analysis for farmers

Variables	Coefficient	Standard error	P-value
Tibiofemoral angle	0.0009	0.209	0.403
Intercept	17.965	8.634	0.403

Body mass index (BMI) reading is an indicator for weight status and it is usually put into three categories; less than 25 kg/m² indicates normal weight, from 25 to 30 kg/m² implies overweight, and greater than 30 indicates obesity. (Yusu, et al., 2011).

In this finding, the mean BMI was 24.85 ± 0.09 kg/m². Most of the patients were within normal weight except few that demonstrated overweight when compared to the mean value and this demonstrated that weight is not a risk factor.

CHAPTER 6

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

6.1 CONCLUSION

Osteoarthritis is a trivial degenerative joint disorder affecting the older population. It is globally recognized as the most prevailing arthritis and a leading cause of disability among the aged. It is a dangerous and life-threatening joint disorder with substantial limitations on day-to-day activities and the value of life of more than millions of people. It mainly affects the hands, hips and knees and often causes weaknesses, disabilities, interferences with one's work and general productivity, with highly unexpected results such as joint replacement and socioeconomic costs.

Osteoarthritis is a multifactorial disease whose aetiology is not fully understood. Several studies had linked the progression of the disease to many risk factors which includes age, weight, lack of vitamin D, previous injury, malalignment, trauma and occupations that demand climbing, squatting and lifting of heavy loads.

Due to increasing age and rise in obesity of the general population, the level of prevalence, health implications, and economic repercussions of osteoarthritis are likely to rise drastically. Hence this study presented the biophysics osteoarthritis of the lateral compartment with valgus knee deformity (knock-knee): a case study among Ghanaian elderly women within an urban orthopaedic practice. The objective was to determine the effect of loading on the lateral compartment of the knee joints in relation to occupation. The results obtained showed that the degree of deformity was associated with occupation that entailed vigorous physical activities. The study also predicted that a site of deformity, either left or right knee could be as a result of joints which were being placed under a repetitive stress for a longer duration, thereby causing more loads to be exerted on the joints in progression of the disease.

Finally, this study did not agree with the hypothesis that age and weight are risk factors of osteoarthritis. This was evident when there was no correlation between the maligned angle, the age and the weight.

6.2 RECOMMENDATIONS

6.2.1 Policy making

Osteoarthritis is a disability which had no cure, but measures can be put in place to prevent the onset and development of the disease. With Ghana's population experiencing a rise in age and obesity, the level of prevalence, healthcare implications and economic outcomes associated with osteoarthritis are likely to experience a dramatic increase. So far, there are no national data on the disease; hence the need to kick-start the requisite research and evaluations in order to understand the burden of the disease, the risk factors associated with it and come with possible and effective strategies to serve as intervention.

Regular programmes such as weight management, self-management education, light aerobic activities and muscle strengthening exercises should be encouraged among individuals so as to help in the prevention and treatment of osteoarthritis.

Working environments should be upgraded by introducing policies and measures that would help impede the occurrence of osteoarthritis.

6.2.2 Further research on the study

Further research needs to be conducted on this study where by lifetime histories of occupational exposures and other suspected risk factors in the workplace of the subjects should be detailed.

Both genders should be included to better understand the relationship between occupation and joint loadings, age and weight gain.

REFERENCES

- Alhambra, D. P., Judge, A., Javaid, M. K., Cooper, C., Diez-Perez, A., & Arden, N. K. (2014). Incidence and risk factors for clinically diagnosed knee, hip and hand osteoarthritis: influences of age, gender and osteoarthritis affecting other joints. *Ann Rheum Dis*, 1659-1664.
- Allen, K. D., & Golightly, Y. M. (2015). Epidemiology of osteoarthritis: state of the evidence. *Curr Opin Rheumatol*, 276-283.
- Anderson, J., & Felson, D. (1988). Factors associated with osteoarthritis of the knee in the first national Health and Nutrition Examination Survey (Hanes 1). Evidence for an association with overweight, race, and physical demands of work. *American Journal Epidemiol*, 179-89.
- Behzad, H. (2011). Knee osteoarthritis diagnosis, treatment and associated factors of progression: part II. *Cyprian J Intern Med*, 249-255.
- Bergmann, G., Bender, A., Graichen, F., Dymke, J., Rohlmann, A., Trepczynski, A., . . . Kutzner, I. (2014). Standardized Loads Acting in Knee Implants. *PLoS ONE* 9(1), 1-12.
- Brouwer, G. M., van Tol, A. W., Bergink, A. P., Bernsen, R. M., Reijman, M., Pols, H. A., & Bierma-Zeinstra, S. M. (2007). Association Between Valgus and Varus Alignment and the Development and Progression of Radiographic Osteoarthritis of the Knee. *Arthritis & Rheumatism*, 1204-1211.
- Callahan, L., Cleveland, R., Shreffler, J., Schwartz, T., Schoster, B., Randolph, R., . . . Jordan, J. (2011). Association of educational attainment, occupation and community poverty with knee osteoarthritis in the Johnston County (North Carolina) osteoarthritis project. *Arthritis Res Ther*, 13(5): R169.

- Cerejo, R., Dunlop, D., Cahue, S., Channin, D., Song, J., & Sharma, L. (2002). The Influence of Alignment on Risk of Knee Osteoarthritis Progression According to Baseline stage of Disease. *Arthritis & Rheumatism*, 2632-2636.
- Cleveland, R., Schwartz TA, Prizer, L., Randolph, R., Schoster, B., Renner, J., . . . Callahan, L. (2013). Association of educational attainment, occupation, and community poverty with hip osteoarthritis. *Arthritis Care Res (Hoboken)*, 65:954-61.
- Croft, P., Coggon, D., Cruddas, M., & Cooper, C. (1992). Osteoarthritis of the hip: an occupational disease in farmers. *BMJ*, 1269-72.
- Dillon, C., Rasch, E., Gu, Q., & Hirsch, R. (2006). Prevalence of knee osteoarthritis in the United States: arthritis data from the Third National Health and Nutrition Examination Survey 1991-94. *J Rheumatol*, 33 (11):2271-9.
- Englund, M., Guermazi, A., Gale, D., Hunter, D., Aliabadi, P., Clancy, M., & Felson, D. (2008). Incidental meniscal findings on knee MRI in middle-aged and elderly persons. *N Engl J Med*, 359(11):1108-15.
- Felson, D. T. (2003). Osteoarthritis of the Knee. *The New England Journal of Medicine*, 1-8.
- Felson, D. T. (2006). Osteoarthritis of the knee. *The New England Journal of Medicine*, 1-8.
- Felson, D. T., Nui, J., Gross, D. K., Englund, M., Sharma, L., Cooke, D. T., . . . Nevitt, M. C. (2013). Valgus Malalignment Is a Risk Factor for Lateral Knee Osteoarthritis Incidence and Progression. *Arthritis & Rheumatism*, 355-362.
- Felson, D., Hanna, M., Naimark, A., Berkeley, J., Gordon, G., Wilson, P., & Anderson, J. (1991). Occupational physical demands, knee bending, and knee osteoarthritis: results from the Framingham Study. *Journal Rheumatol*, 1587-92.

- Felson, D., Lawrence, R., Dieppe, P., Hirsch, R., Helmick, C., Jordan, J., . . . Sowers, M. (2000). Osteoarthritis: New Insights Part 1 : The Disease and its Risk Factors. *Annals of Internal Medicine*, 1-12.
- Felson, D., Zhang, Y., Anthony, J., Naimark, A., & Anderson, J. (1992). Weight Loss Reduces the Risk for Symptomatic Knee Osteoarthritis in Women: The Framingham Study. *Ann Intern Med*, 116:535–9.
- Giles, W., & Klippel, J. H. (2010). *A National Public Health Agenda for Osteoarthritis*. Centers for Disease Control and Prevention.
- Hanna, F., Wluka, A., Bell, R., Davis, S., & Cicuttini, F. (2004). Osteoarthritis and the postmenopausal woman: Epidemiological, magnetic resonance imaging, and radiological findings. *Semin Arthritis Rheum*, 34(3):631-6.
- Hardcastle, S., Dieppe, P., Gregson, C., Arden, N., Spector, T., Hart, D., . . . Tobias, J. (2015). Individuals with high bone mass have an increased prevalence of radiographic knee osteoarthritis. *Bone*, 71:171-179.
- Hardcastle, S., Dieppe, P., Gregson, C., Hunter, D., Thomas, G., Arden, N., . . . Tobias, J. (2014). Prevalence of radiographic hip osteoarthritis is increased in high bone mass. *Osteoarthritis Cartilage*, 22(8):1120-8.
- Hosnijeh, F. S., Runhaar, J., Meurs, J. B., & Bierma-Zeinstra, S. M. (2015). Biomarkers for osteoarthritis: Can they be used for risk assessment? A systematic review. *Elsevier*, 1-14.
- Hunter, D., Nui, J., Felson, D., Harvey, W., Gross, K., McCree, P., . . . Zhang, Y. (2007). Knee alignment does not predict incident osteoarthritis: the Framingham osteoarthritis study. *Arthritis Rheum*, 56(4):1212-8.

- Hussain, S., Neilly, D., Baliga, S., Patil, S., & Meek, R. (2016). Knee osteoarthritis: a review of management options. *Scottish Medical Journal*, 1-10.
- Ilori, T., Ladipo, M., Ogunbode, A., & Obimakinde, A. (2016). Knee Osteoarthritis and perceived social support amongst patients in a family medicine clinic. *South African Family Practice*, 202-206.
- Issa, S. N., & Sharma, L. (2006). Epidemiology of Osteoarthritis: aAn Update. *Current Rheumatology Reports*, 7-15.
- Jiang, L., Tian, W., Wang, Y., Rong, J., Bao, C., Lui, Y., . . . Wang, C. (2011). Body mass index and susceptibility to knee osteoarthritis: A systematic review and meta-analysis. *Society of French of Rheumatology*, 1-7.
- Johnson, V. L., & Hunter, D. J. (2014). The epidemiology of osteoarthritis. *Best Practice & Reserach Clinical Rheumatology*, 5-15.
- Jordan, J., Helmick, C., Renner, J., Luta, G., Dragomir, A., Woodard, J., . . . Hochberg, M. (2007). Prevalence of knee symptoms and radiographic and symptomatic knee osteoarthritis in African Americans and Caucasians: the Johnston County Osteoarthritis Project. *J Rheumatol*, 34(1):172:80.
- Kaufman, K., AN, K., Litchy, W., Morrey, B., & Chao, E. (1991). Dynamic joint forces during knee isokinetic exercise. *Am J Sports Med*, 19(3):305-16.
- Kazemi, S. M., Minaei, R., Safdari, F., Keipourfard, A., Forghani, R., & Mirzapourshafiei, A. (2015). Supercondylar Osteotomy in Valgus Knee: Angle Blade Plate Versus Locking Compression Plate. *Archive of Bone and Joint Surgery*, 29-34.
- Kellgren, J., & Lawrence, J. (1957). Radiological Assessment of Osteo-arthritis. *Ann Rheum Dis*, 494-502.

- Kerkhof, H., Lories, R., Meulenbelt, I., Jonsdottir, I., Valdes, A., Arp, P., . . . Helgi Jonsson. (2010). A Genome-Wide Association Study Identifies an Osteoarthritis Susceptibility Locus on Chromosome 7q22. *American College of Rheumatology*, 499-510.
- Khan, H., Aitken, D., Chou, L., McBride, A., Ding, C., Blizzard, L., . . . Jones, G. (2014). A family history of knee joint replacement increases the progression of knee radiographic osteoarthritis and medial tibial cartilage volume loss over 10 years. *Osteoarthritis Cartilage*, 23(2):203-9.
- Kumar, D., Manal, K., & Rudolph, K. (2012). Knee joint loading during gait in healthy controls and individuals with knee osteoarthritis. *osteoarthritis Research Society International*, 1-12.
- Lane, N., Hochberg, M., Pressman, A., Scott, J., & Nevitt, M. (1999). Recreational physical activity and the risk of osteoarthritis of the hip in elderly women. *J Rheumatol*, 26(4):849-54.
- Lohmander, L., Gerhardsson de Verdier, M., Rollof, J., Nilsson, P., & Engström, G. (2009). Incidence of severe knee and hip osteoarthritis in relation to different measures of body mass: a population-based prospective cohort study. *Ann Rheum Dis.*, 68(4):490-6.
- Lohmander, L., Ostenberg, A., Englund, M., & Roos, H. (2004). High prevalence of knee osteoarthritis, pain, and functional limitations in female soccer players twelve years after anterior cruciate ligament injury. *Arthritis Rheum*, 50(10):3145-52.
- Maly, M. R., Costigan, P. A., & Olney, S. J. (2006). Determinants of Self-Report Outcome Measures in People With Knee Osteoarthritis. *the American Congress of Rehabilitation Medicine and the American Academy of Physical Medicine and Rehabilitation*, 1-9.

- Manek, N. J., & Lane, N. E. (2000). Osteoarthritis: Current Concepts in Diagnosis and Management. *Am Fam Physician*, 1795-1804.
- Martin, U. (2005). *Chronic Knee Pain in the Elderly*. London: Arthritis Research Campaign.
- McAlindon, T., Jacques, P., Hannan, M., Aliabadi, P., Weissman, B., Rush, D., . . . Felson, D. (1996). Do antioxidant micronutrients protect against the development and progression of knee osteoarthritis? *Arthritis Rheum*, 39(4):648-56.
- Mcalindon, T., Jacques, P., Zhang, Y., Hannan, M., Aliabadi, P., Weissman, B., . . . Felson, D. (1996). Do Antioxidant Micronutrints Protect Against The Development And Progression Of Knee Osteoarthritis. *Arthritis & Rheumatism*, 648-656.
- McAlindon, T., Wilson, P., Aliabadi, P., Weissman, B., & Felson, D. (1999). Level of physical activity and the risk of radiographic and symptomatic knee osteoarthritis in the elderly: the Framingham study. *Am J Med*, 106(2):151-7.
- Moreland, J., Bassett, L., & Hanker, G. (1987). Radiographic analysis of the axial alignment of the lower extremity. *J Bone Joint Surg Am*, 69(5):745-9.
- Murphy, L., & Helmick, C. (2012). The Impact of Osteoarthritis in the United States: A Population -Health Perspective. *American Journal of Nursing*, 1-7.
- Naeem, N. (2014). Evidence-based practice and mangement of Archiritis in the Upper West Region of Ghana: Challenges in implementation and practice. 1-114.
- Nelson, A., Braga, L., Renner, J., Atashili, J., Woodard, J., hchberg, M., . . . Jordan, J. (2010). Characterixation of Individual radiographic features of Hip Osteoarthritis in African American and White women and Men: The Johnston County Osteoarthritis Project. *Arthritis Care & research*, 190-197.

- Neogi, T., & Zhang, Y. (2013). Epidemiology of Osteoarthritis. *Rheum Dis Clin North Am*, 1-19.
- Neogi, T., Booth, S., Zhang, Y., Jacques, P., Terkeltaub, R., Aliabadi, P., & Felson, D. (2006). Low Vitamin K Status Is Associated With Osteoarthritis in the Hand and Knee. *Arthritis & Rheumatism*, 1255-1261.
- Nevitt, M., Felson, D., Williams, E., & Grady, D. (2001). The effect of estrogen plus progestin on knee symptoms and related disability in postmenopausal women: The Heart and Estrogen/Progestin Replacement Study, a randomized, double-blind, placebo-controlled trial. *Arthritis Rheum*, 44(4):811-8.
- Newberry, S. J., Fitzgerald, J. D., Maglione, M. A., O'Hanlon, C. E., Booth, M., Motala, A., . . . Shekelle, P. G. (2015). *Systematic Review for Effectiveness of Hyaluronic Acid in the Treatment of Severe Degenerative Joint Disease (DJD) of the Knee*. Rockville, Maryland.
- Nisell, R., Ericson, M., Németh, G., & Ekholm, J. (1999). Tibiofemoral joint forces during isokinetic knee extension. *Am J Sports Med.*, 17(1):49-54.
- Pan, F., Ding, C., Winzenberg, T., Khan, H., Martel-Pelletier, J., Pelletier, P., . . . Graeme, J. (2014). The offspring of people with a total knee replacement for severe primary knee osteoarthritis have a higher risk of worsening knee pain over 8 years. *Ann Rheum Dis*.
- Peat, G., Thomas, E., Duncan, R., & Wood, L. (2010). Is a "False-Positive" Clinical Diagnosis of Knee Osteoarthritis Just the Early Diagnosis of Pre-Radiographic Disease? *Arthritis Care & Research* , 1502-1506.
- Pfleger, B., & Woolf, A. (2003). Burden of major musculoskeletal conditions. *World Health Organization*, 646-656.

- Roos, E., Ostenberg, A., Roos, H., Ekdahl, C., & Lohmander, L. (2001). Long-term outcome of meniscectomy: symptoms, function, and performance tests in patients with or without radiographic osteoarthritis compared to matched controls. *Osteoarthritis Cartilage*, 9(4):316-24.
- Scott, C. E., Nutton, R. W., & Biant, L. C. (2013). Lateral compartment osteoarthritis of the knee. *The Bone & Joint journal*, 436-44.
- Sharma, L. (2007). The Role of Varus and Valgus Alignment in Knee Osteoarthritis. *Arthritis & Rheumatism*, 1044-1047.
- Sharma, L., Song, J., Felson, D. T., Cahue, S., Shamiyeh, E., & Dunlop, D. (2001). The Role of Knee Alignment in Disease Progression and Functional Decline in Knee Osteoarthritis. *JAMA*, 188-95.
- Sharma, L., Song, J., Felson, D., Shamiyeh, E., & Dunlop, D. (2001). The Roles of Knee Alignment in Disease Progression and Functional Decline in Knee . *American Medical Association*, 1-8.
- Shelburne, K., & Pandy, M. (2002). A dynamic model of the knee and lower limb for simulating rising movements. *Comput Methods Biomech Biomed Engin.*, 5(2):149-59.
- Srikanth, V., Fryer, J., Zhai, G., Winzenberg, T., Hosmer, D., & Jones, G. (2005). A meta-analysis of sex differences prevalence, incidence and severity of osteoarthritis. *Osteoarthritis Cartilage*, 13(9):769-81.
- Tang, X., Wang, S., Zhan, S., Niu, J., Tao, K., Zhang, Y., & Lin, J. (2015). The prevalence of Symptomatic Knee Osteoarthritis in China. *American College of Rheumatology*, 648-653.

Tetsworth, K., & Paley, D. (1994). Malalignment and Degenerative Arthropathy. *Orthopedic Clinics of North America*, 1-12.

WHO. (2003). *The Burden of Musculoskeletal Conditions at the Start of the Millennium*. Geneva: WHO Library Cataloguing-in-Publication.

Wilk, K., Escamilla, R., Fleisig, G., Barrentine, S., Andrews, J., & Boyd, M. (1996). A comparison of tibiofemoral joint forces and electromyographic activity during open and closed kinetic chain exercises. *Am J Sports Med*, 24(4):518:27.

Zhang, W. (2010). Risk factors of knee osteoarthritis--excellent evidence but little has been done. *Osteoarthritis Cartilage*, 18(1):1-2.

Zhang, Y., & Jordan, J. (2010). Epidemiology of Osteoarthritis. *Clin Geriatr Med*, 355-369.

Zhang, Y., Xu, L., Nevitt, M., Aliabadi, P., Yu, W., Qin, M., . . . Felson, D. (2001). Comparison of the Prevalence of Knee Osteoarthritis Between the Ederly Chinese Population in Beijing and Whites in the United States. *Arthritis & Rheumatism*, 2065-2071.

WHO. See (<http://www.who.int/mediacentre/factsheets/fs311/en/index.html>).

Boston Children's Hospital. www.childrenshospital.org/conditions-and-treatments/conditions/k/knock-knee. Assessed: 25/05/2018

https://www.indexmundi.com/ghana/demographics_profile.html. Assessed: 25/05/2018

“Swollen Knee”<https://www.mayoclinic.org/diseases-conditions/swollen-knee/symptoms-causes/syc-20378129>. Assessed: 02/06/2018

https://www.physio-pedia.com/Total_knee_arthroplasty. Assessed: 03/06/2018

<https://www.weightwatchers.com/au/healthyweightrangechart>. Assessed: 15/06/2018

<https://www.scribd.com/presentation/112853777/Chapter-1-Mechanics-of-the-Body>.

Assessed: 16/06/2018

<http://goasodiocese.org/2016-01-07-09-04-40/institutions/130-st-john-of-god-hospital>.

Assessed: 25/05/2018

APPENDICES

Appendix A

Table 1: Index, age, weight, angle, force, height and occupation of subjects.

Index	Age/yr	Weight/kg	Height/m	TBF/θ	MAD/θ	Degree of deformity/θ	Occupation
1	59	103	2.01	11.1	18.6	8.6	Unemployed
2	54	76	1.76	23.7	44.7	34.7	Teacher
3	59	71	1.68	18.2	36.1	26.1	Farmer
4	53	68	1.66	17.3	35.6	25.6	Trader
5	70	70	1.67	19.1	36	36	Farmer
6	80	49	1.47	17.9	33.6	33.6	Trader
7	70	60	1.54	6.4	15.6	25.6	Unemployed
8	66	56	1.5	16	24.2	34.2	Farmer
9	44	110	2.04	7.5	13.6	3.6	Civil servant
10	46	59	1.54	18.7	37.1	27.1	Farmer
11	72	62	1.58	8.4	17.8	17.8	Trader
12	47	57	1.55	21.8	29.7	19.7	Farmer
13	55	52	1.48	11.4	25.6	15.6	Farmer
14	56	75	1.76	20.7	22.9	12.9	Teacher
15	80	72	1.7	22.9	32.9	22.9	Trader
16	51	80	1.83	23	27.1	7.1	Trader
17	47	68	1.65	6.8	18.1	8.1	Teacher
18	59	92	1.94	12.6	18.5	8.5	Farmer
19	70	55	1.49	13	13.6	3.6	Farmer

20	59	49	1.47	13.5	31.8	21.8	Farmer
21	63	68	1.65	6.6	15.5	5.5	Trader
22	53	86	1.9	8.1	24	14	Farmer
23	46	78	1.81	8.4	18.2	8.2	Trader
24	40	68	1.65	18.1	21.6	11.6	Farmer
25	57	60	1.55	13.3	31.8	21.8	Farmer
26	64	68	1.65	11.4	15.3	5.3	Farmer
27	81	65	1.61	13.3	23.9	23.9	Farmer
28	56	90	1.93	5.6	17.3	17.3	Trader
29	72	61	1.56	15.3	19.7	9.7	Retired
30	48	87	1.91	30.9	47.7	37.7	Trader
31	60	65	1.61	9	12.1	32.1	Trader
32	44	110	2.04	6.3	15.9	15.9	Trader
33	52	80	1.83	9.2	22.3	12.3	Trader
34	44	67	1.64	9.6	24.8	14.8	Civil Servant
35	41	71	1.68	9.4	23.4	23.4	Trader
36	63	78	1.81	6.1	16.5	16.5	Trader
37	46	59	1.54	7.1	15.2	15.2	Teacher
38	53	68	1.65	12.4	33.2	23.2	Trader
39	58	96	1.96	8.8	26	16	Trader
40	61	70	1.67	7.1	19.1	9.1	Trader
41	45	120	2.08	13	37.7	37.7	Housewife
42	40	75	1.75	7	17.8	17.8	Trader
43	59	76	1.79	12.8	27.8	17.8	Trader

44	40	90	1.91	9	20.4	20.4	Trader
45	51	75	1.75	12.4	17.6	7.6	Trader
46	53	100	2	8.3	21.5	21.5	Unemployed
47	66	109	2.05	8.3	18.7	12.7	Farmer
48	43	105	2.03	7.9	18	18	Trader
49	50	95	1.95	6.3	18.9	28.9	Farmer
50	59	81	1.84	8.3	17.9	17.9	Trader
51	60	100	2	7.1	12.5	2.5	Trader
52	49	68	1.65	13.4	27.2	17.2	Farmer
53	58	73	1.73	8.4	14.8	14.8	Teacher
54	44	84	1.87	10.7	21.8	11.8	Trader
55	62	65	1.61	7.7	15.4	15.4	Trader
56	51	66	1.62	14.7	42.9	32.9	Trader
57	59	90	1.91	13.4	28.8	18.8	Farmer
58	68	69	1.66	21.9	45.1	35.1	Farmer
59	58	67	1.64	33.1	34.9	24.9	Caterer
60	64	97	1.95	17.5	27.2	17.2	Farmer
61	45	128	2.08	8.7	14.9	4.9	
62	47	110	2.06	14.7	26.7	16.7	
63	49	104	2	36.6	49.5	9.5	
64	74	63	1.59	27.1	34	24	Trader
65	55	100	2	12.3	37	27	Trader
66	56	78	1.81	8.4	19.9	19.9	Trader
67	42	81	1.82	11.3	18.6	8.6	Nurse

68	46	70	1.69	16.4	31.9	6.4	Farmer
69	56	62	1.58	12.3	37.3	27.3	Farmer
70	50	78	1.79	14.7	27.7	17.7	Trader
71	67	75	1.75	8	15	32	Unemployed
72	59	82	1.83	9.4	21.5	25.5	Farmer
73	58	58	1.52	11.1	22.1	12.1	
74	60	75	1.75	10	22.4	22.4	Farmer
75	83	74	1.74	16.8	36.7	26.7	Unemployed
76	62	92	1.92	6.1	13.2	13.2	Farmer
77	52	95	1.95	23.8	29.9	9.9	Trader
78		60	1.55	5.1	13.9	13.9	
79	48	96	1.96	13.1	19.3	9.3	Trader
80	47	114	2.07	15.8	32.8	22.8	Trader
81	64	70	1.67	11.3	22.6	12.6	Farmer
82	48	75	1.75	8.3	19.3	29.3	Trader
83	61	67	1.64	13.4	28.8	-1.2	Farmer
84	50	90	1.91	27.2	35.8	25.8	Seamstress
85	68	55	1.48	14.5	27.1	17.1	Unemployed
86	50	76	1.76	9.6	16.7	6.7	Trader
87	50	74	1.74	13.8	34.9	24.9	Trader
88	68	57	1.51	18.5	28.8	8.8	Farmer
89	47	82	1.83	11.6	26.3	16.3	Trader
90	65	105	2.03	9.7	27.1	17.1	Farmer

Table 2: X-component force, Y-component force, RF, and BMI

X-force	Y-force	RF	BMI
9.96	102.52	103	25.49
15.61	74.38	76	24.54
11.23	70.11	71	25.16
10.23	67.23	68	24.68
11.61	69.03	70	25.10
7.62	48.4	49	22.68
3.35	59.91	60	25.30
7.79	55.46	56	24.89
7.19	109.76	110	26.43
9.59	58.22	59	24.88
4.54	61.83	62	24.84
10.78	55.97	57	23.73
5.16	51.74	52	23.74
13.47	73.78	75	24.21
14.29	70.57	72	24.91
15.95	78.39	80	23.89
4.03	67.88	68	24.98
10.1	91.44	92	24.44
6.23	54.65	55	24.77
5.76	48.66	49	22.68
3.91	67.89	68	24.98
6.07	85.79	86	23.82

5.71	77.79	78	23.81
10.7	67.15	68	24.98
6.95	59.6	60	24.97
6.75	67.66	68	24.98
7.53	64.56	65	25.08
4.4	89.89	90	24.16
8.12	60.46	61	25.07
23.18	83.86	87	23.85
5.1	64.8	65	25.08
6.04	109.83	110	26.43
6.42	79.74	80	23.89
5.61	66.77	67	24.91
5.82	70.76	71	25.16
4.15	77.89	78	23.81
3.65	58.89	59	24.88
7.34	67.6	68	24.98
7.37	95.72	96	24.99
4.33	69.87	70	25.10
13.58	119.23	120	27.74
4.58	74.86	75	24.49
8.47	75.53	76	23.72
7.06	89.72	90	24.67
8.1	74.56	75	24.49
7.24	99.74	100	25.00

7.89	108.71	109	25.94
7.23	104.75	105	25.48
5.22	94.86	95	24.98
5.86	80.79	81	23.92
6.19	99.81	100	25.00
7.93	67.54	68	24.98
5.35	72.8	73	24.39
7.83	83.63	84	24.02
4.36	64.85	65	25.08
8.44	65.46	66	25.15
10.5	89.39	90	24.67
13.11	67.74	69	25.04
19.09	64.22	67	24.91
14.76	95.87	97	25.51
9.71	127.63	128	29.59
14.07	109.1	110	25.92
32.66	98.74	104	26.00
14.76	61.25	63	24.92
10.71	99.42	100	25.00
5.71	77.79	78	23.81
7.97	80.61	81	24.45
19.24	67.31	70	24.51
6.64	61.64	62	24.84
9.98	77.36	78	24.34

5.23	74.82	75	24.49
6.72	81.72	82	24.49
5.61	57.73	58	25.10
6.54	74.71	75	24.49
10.81	73.21	74	24.44
4.9	91.87	92	24.96
19.59	92.96	95	24.98
2.67	59.94	60	24.97
10.95	95.37	96	24.99
15.67	112.92	114	26.61
6.89	69.66	70	25.10
5.43	74.8	75	24.49
7.82	66.54	67	24.91
21.16	87.48	90	24.67
6.94	54.56	55	25.11
6.36	75.73	76	24.54
8.89	73.46	74	24.44
9.16	56.26	57	25.00
8.29	81.58	82	24.49
8.88	104.62	105	25.48